

International Deputation Report

***International Expert Consultation (IEC) on
Building the CIARD Framework for Data and
Information Sharing at Beijing, China***

20-23 June 2011

Submitted by

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- 4. Name of the conference attended** International Expert Consultation on 'Building the
CIARD Framework for Data and Information
Sharing"
- 5. Venue and date of the conference** Beijing, June 20-23 2011

6. Highlights of the conference (including other participants role in it)

The Global Forum on Agricultural Research (GFAR) in association with the Chinese Academy of Agricultural Science (CAAS), organized International Expert Consultation (IEC) on Building the 'CIARD' (Coherence in Information for Agricultural Research for Development) Framework for Data and Information sharing during June 20-23 2011 at Beijing for the CIARD partners. Nearly 50 experts from around the world have participated in the consultation and I was the official nominee of the Department of Agricultural Research and Education (DARE) representing Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR) in the consultation.

On the first day of the consultation, June 20th 2011, an 'Infoshare Marketplace' was organized, where participants shared their organizations experiences in sharing data and information. Twenty four organizations shared their experiences at the Infoshare Marketplace. On behalf of ICAR, I have displayed a poster prepared by me with the title '**Data and Information Sharing in NARS**' in which I have made a collage of website screen shots of the data and information sharing products developed by various constituents of National Agricultural Research System (NARS) of India.

On the second day, June 21st 2011, in the inaugural session, introductory statements were made by the organizers *viz.*, Mark Holderness (GFAR), Stephen Rudgard (FAO)

and Liu Xu (CAAS) about the need of the data and information sharing in agriculture, what we are sharing and what need to share. After the statements, Prof. Liu Xu, Vice President, CAAS launched the CIARD website in Chinese <<http://www.ciard.net/zh-hans>> which is being maintained by the Institute of Information Sciences of CAAS and in the initial phase, twenty five agriculture research and innovation institutes along with the Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences are participating in it as CIARD partners. After website launch, the summary of E-Consultation hosted by the Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO) on the E-Agriculture community site <<http://www.e-agriculture.org>> was made by Tom Baker.

In the summary, Tom Baker presented that the e-consultation had more than 400 contributions from participants from 162 countries and suggested that the framework has to consider issues including:-

- (a) Enabling more open data repositories and standards.
- (b) Enabling national and institutional policies that contribute to more open availability, accessibility, applicability and effective use of data and information from public domain agricultural research at all levels from global to local communities.
- (c) Building new capacities to generate, manage and publish data and information more openly.
- (d) Creating “meta-data” or descriptive data using standard vocabularies and “amalgamators” of these meta-data, leveraging concepts such as of “Linked Data” through URLs, developing core data sets that may be useful in meeting the ARD challenges.
- (e) Considering institutional concerns about the use of their data especially in intellectual property and ownership.
- (f) Considering the underlying need of collaboration and partnership in managing ARD data and information.

Then after the tea break, Tom Baker had done presentation about Linked Open Data taking BBC website <<http://www.bbc.co.uk>> as example and showed how the information could be shared through interoperable data. He informed that the Linked Data is not an all-or-nothing proposition but a continuum starting, at the low end, with simple choices.

He presented what Tim Berners-Lee had summarized about the Linked Data approach as a pathway leading information providers towards progressively higher levels of interoperability:-

*	On the Web, open licenses.	Make your stuff available on the Web, in whatever format, under open licenses.
**	Machine-readable data.	Make your stuff available as machine readable structured data; a table in Excel is better than just an image of the same.
***	Non-proprietary format.	Use plain Comma-Separated-Values format (CSV) in preference to Excel.
****	RDF standards.	Use URLs (URIs) to identify your things so that people can point to them, and describe them using RDF.
*****	Linked RDF.	Link your data to other people's data to provide context and add value.

During post lunch session on 21st June, 2011, working groups were made and modalities are provided. Johannes Keizer (FAO) briefed about the technical issues and Ajit Maru (GFAR) about institutional issues that should be considered in the framework development. Four groups were made and each two groups discussed on the topics. Viz., 1. Priority Services and Capacities; 2. Tools, Standards and Infrastructure.

After the discussions, during plenary, presentation of outputs from working group - Priority Services and Capacities were made which was facilitated by Stephen Rudgard and Viviana Palmieri. Another two groups presented on Tools, Standards and Infrastructure which was facilitated by Qiaoqiao Zhang. After the groups' presentation, there was a plenary presentation on status of interoperability standards (from e-consultation) and it was followed by discussion. After that Valeria Pesce spoken on the topic 'CIARD-RING, now and in the future', Johannes Keizer gave presentation on 'agINFRA and its contribution to CIARD' and Tom Baker on RDF, and what we can get from RDF.

On Wednesday 22nd June, 2011, there was a presentation from Meng Xianxue on National Systems - Perspectives from China to be considered in the Framework Development. And after that the working groups met again and discussed on the 'Next Steps - Action Points' to the issues discussed on previous day and during the plenary

presentation, outputs were made which was facilitated by Simon Wilkinson. During the post lunch session under the Chairpersonship of Pan Shuchun, few case studies on examples of sharing research data/information, focusing on innovative aspects viz., VIVO by John Ferreira, CABI - future plans by Zhang QiaoQiao, AGRIS - future plans by Johannes Keizer, GAINS by Joel Sam, Review and outlook of National Agriculture Data Center: Key technology and data resources by Zhou Guomin and Crop germplasm resources (CGR) information sharing in China by Fang Wei were presented.

On Thursday 23rd June, 2011, the final day, the groups discussed on 'Agendas for Action' and reported during the plenary which was preceded by the presentation on China agricultural informationalization in rural areas by Mei Fangquan before the plenary. Stephen Rudgard and Ajit Maru facilitated discussions on preparation of draft statements of outcomes and agendas for action from the Workshop. During the concluding session, closing statements from organizers on future events, links to GCARD process and to other major initiatives were made by CAAS, FAO and GFAR.

7. Summary of the scientific contribution by the deputed scientist including any special discussion points at the conference

A poster with the title '**Data and Information Sharing in NARS**' which is a collage of all website screen shots of the data and information sharing products developed by various constituents of NARS was exhibited at 'Infoshare Marketplace' and during the consultation, same information was presented when the groups met for discussions and the group members were apprised about the current scenario of data and information sharing in NARS. For the IEC, summary papers were called and I have submitted a paper on '**Information and Data Sharing in NARS of India**' which is available at http://www.fao.org/docs/eims/upload/295329/4741_Information_and_Data_Sharing_in_NARS_of_India-Sridhar_Gutam.pdf.

8. Recommendation/Conclusions arrived at the conference

The participants at the consultation identified priority actions for the development of the framework, drawing on the findings of an E-Consultation event hosted by FAO on the -Agriculture community website. They also agreed that the current key concept in data and information sharing is interoperability and 'Linked Open Data'. When the data or information is Interoperable, then it can easily be retrieved, processed, re-used, and

re-packaged (“operated”) by other systems/machines, and Linked Data <<http://linkeddata.org/>> approaches use the Web to connect related resources that weren't previously linked. The “Open Data” movement <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_Data> aims to make data freely available to everyone, and the CIARD movement shares this ideal and is working to make agricultural research information publicly available and accessible to all. The participants agreed that they would register various services of their respective organizations on CIARD RING. The participants opined that achieving the ideal objective of sharing all global data as “Interoperable Linked Open Data” will be a gradual process that will develop in stages at a varying pace in different organizations and countries and they would advocate and work for the same.

The CIARD consultation at Beijing examined in some detail the three main areas that need to be resolved in building the framework for data and information:-

- (a) Harnessing of the rapidly evolving technologies around linked open data concepts.
- (b) Provision of organizational support so that interoperable linked data is openly available.
- (c) Advocacy for and emergence of a coherent global community involved in agricultural innovation and that shares and uses data appropriately.

The IEC also recognized that collaboration and partnerships at various levels worldwide are key to effective sharing of data and information for agricultural innovation and thus building trust and institutional structures to bring this collaboration and partnerships must be a part of the framework. Information and communications management (ICM) in agriculture is poor globally with low investment and weak capacities, and the framework will contribute for its strengthening.

9. Conclusion

The ICAR being a partner of CIARD, should make efforts for registering all its institutes' data and information sharing services and also should influence other constituents of NARS of the country for the same. When this is achieved, a one stop portal of data and information sharing on agricultural research in India would be in place. The global recognition of our country, India, as an emerging economic power is also a major global

knowledge hub for agriculture and environment and it would shortly be among the 10 major producers of agricultural and environmental information. Thus the appropriate management of agricultural knowledge is need of the hour as Agriculture Commons. When there is a clear link between availability of information (including data) in a society openly it increases the rate and speed of innovation. This would contribute to the development and growth, both economical and social sector of our rural population of nearly 700 million who are depending on agriculture for their livelihoods and expect rapid alleviation of their hunger and poverty through inclusive growth and development.

The developments in open access field worldwide and also India would demand for efforts to make data and information in open access. When both the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR) and the International Crop Research Institute for Semi-arid Tropics (ICRISAT) had mandated Open Access policy for the public funded research, the same is due in ICAR and NARS. Though there are some efforts being made for making agricultural information openly available, accessible and effectively used like the good efforts of ICAR for making its two flagship journals in Open Access and establishment of Institutional Repositories at IARI, CMFRI, IISR and IIHR, much more is needed like influencing all the 79 professional societies, all the institutes/universities to establish repositories. The universities like UAS, Dharwad and KAU, Vellayanikera had made its journals as open access long before ICAR established its “e-pubs” platform.

Many of the conventionally printed publications available are being made available in electronic form on ICAR Institute websites are not searchable and hence cannot be queried. The Robots of Machines cannot read much of the information made available on websites. These websites do not use the available tools and techniques of information that have now started to further enable and enrich the access to specific information on the Internet. The data needed to collaborate and integrate our capabilities in agricultural research and innovation is poorly organized and not easily accessible for regular use. Many of the efforts initiated by ICAR in improving information and data management and its access have not fructified.

It is therefore it is strongly suggested that ICAR may look at making agricultural information (including data) more openly available, accessible and applicable for

effective use appropriately by all involved in agriculture, from input providers, farmers, market intermediaries and consumers as also to those that support and are stakeholders for innovation in agriculture and farming.

10. Recommendations

The following are the recommendations which may be taken up in ICAR/NARS:-

- I. DARE/ICAR mandates that all information (including data) generated through financial support by DARE/ICAR and/or other organizations under Govt. of India be openly available and accessible through appropriate organization through the Internet.
- II. DARE/ICAR develops appropriate coordination with mechanisms for sharing of information in, across and outside the organizations it manages and supports, including Central and State Agricultural Universities, in the country.
- III. DARE/ICAR increases efforts in improving the applicability of information for agricultural innovation in the country and ushers in more emphasis in ensuring that agricultural communities can make effective use of the information.

These suggestions are broad but these are building blocks for some directive principles in building a national strategy for managing information and knowledge related to agriculture. I am confident that if these suggestions, if implemented through appropriate mechanism, would be having far reaching consequences on the function and structure of agricultural research and innovation systems in our country.

11. Any important discussions held by the deputed scientist with other scientists/agencies during or outside the conference.

An informal meeting was held with the officials from FAO and associated with CIARD to have a workshop exclusively for the leaders/researchers from NARS on data and information sharing at New Delhi during International Conference on Innovative Approaches for Agricultural Knowledge Management (November 9-12, 2011).

12. Other visits associated with the conference.

A field trip to Summer Palace was organized on 23rd June, 2011 afternoon.

(Sridhar Gutam)

Data and Information Sharing in NARS of India

The India's National Agricultural Research System is marching towards open access...

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Information and Data Sharing in NARS of India

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I. Management and Sharing of information and Data

The National Agricultural Research System (NARS) of India comprises 97 institutes established by the Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR) and 58 Agricultural Universities established in various states by their respective state governments, or as agriculture faculty in central universities and other autonomous colleges/institutes/universities. While the ICAR institutes are involved in basic and strategic research except few deemed universities which are involved in education, the universities are involved in applied research and education. However, all the institutes and universities have extension activities and training. Substantial research output is produced from these institutes and universities, and they share their research achievements with all of their stakeholders through technical bulletins, leaflets, newsletters, annual reports, books, research highlights, research achievements and research journals. The education and teaching materials are rarely shared with the world. Most of these publications are print only form, and are rarely shared through their websites. Though the institutes and universities share the printed leaflets freely during various training programmes or workshops many of their other publications are priced and are only available upon purchase.

While most of the ICAR institutes make their annual reports and vision documents available online, very few universities (~24%) make them online according to the survey made. In case of peer-reviewed research articles and conference proceedings, only bibliography is made available online that too only by ~35% institutes and ~9% universities on their respective websites. These institutes and universities do not show much importance for sharing the research articles with other stake holders freely. This may be because of the absence of a policy and publication of research articles are seen as individual's job and not of the institutes. There is no provision of reimbursement of pay per page/author pay charges. Exception to this are Central Marine Fisheries Research Institute (CMFRI), Indian Agricultural Research Institute (IARI), Indian Institute of

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Spice Research (IISR) and Indian Institute of Horticultural Research (IIHR) which have established their Institutional Repositories (IRs) to showcase their research and other publications to the world. They are using Free/Open Source Software (FOSS) which is Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) compliant. The repository of CMFRI, 'Eprints@CMFRI' is the most popular repository till date having ~8000 records followed by 'Eprints@IARI' of IARI with ~226 records. Another ICAR institute, the Central Research Institute for Dryland Agriculture (CRIDA) has made all its publications online except that for research articles which can be accessed upon sending email request. For the purpose, CRIDA is providing the email address of an author in the bibliography. Unfortunately, no agricultural university in India has established its repository till date. However, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur has established 'OpenAgri' an open access repository for agricultural research in India under 'Agropedia', a sub-project of World Bank supported National Agricultural Innovation Project (NAIP), and few institutes/universities are utilizing it for depositing their journal articles, book chapters and conference proceedings. Now twelve institutes and universities in NARS are in the process of establishing repositories housing digital collection of rare books and old journals available in their libraries under the NAIP sub-project 'Strengthening of digital library and information management under NARS (e-GRANTH)'. The 'CaneInfo' is a project supported by Department of Scientific and Industrial Research (DSIR) at Sugarcane Breeding Institute (SBI) which acts as a sugarcane repository.

There is at least one scholarly society supported by the institute/ICAR for publication of research journal in respective subject/discipline. These societies organize seminars/symposia/conferences periodically, and also publish the proceedings as supplements to the journal. Though all these publications are in print only form, and are only accessible on subscription either at libraries or with individual subscriptions, few of the societies are making their journal issues accessible to their members, library and consortia upon subscription only with the help of a private web hosting service provider. While the Indian Society of Soil Salinity and Water Quality has uploaded 2009 journal issues online, others are only hosting abstracts and table of contents of forthcoming issues. The scholarly societies are selling their publications for running the business, rather than making them available freely on the web.

Recently under E-Publishing and System for Knowledge Sharing in Agricultural Research (EPSKAR), a sub-project under NAIP, at Directorate of Knowledge Management in Agriculture (DKMA), ICAR has started publishing its two journals viz., Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences and Indian Journal of Animal Sciences as open access journals using Open Journal Systems (OJS) a FOSS software on the <http://epubs.icar.org.in> platform under Indian Agricultural Research Journals. It is also offering hosting support to scholarly societies for making their journals online. Apart from journals, DKMA also brings out various information products of which some are available in e-formats on CD/DVD but all its text books are all in print only formats and are available only on payment.

Few universities (~9%) are also publishing peer-reviewed publications as university research journals. While the Acharya N.G. Ranga Agricultural University is sharing complete issues from 2007 to 2009 by uploading them online, others are only sharing abstracts/table of contents on their websites. However, two universities viz., Kerala Agricultural University and University of Agricultural Sciences, Dharwad are completely publishing them online using OJS. The University of Agricultural Sciences, Bengaluru started to publish its journal online using OJS but could not continue after hosting one as test issue. Scholarly societies in universities are also publishing journals but they are also print only journals except the MASU Journal which is being published using Google sites by the Madras Agricultural Student's Union. Under NAIP sub-project, Consortium for e-Resources in Agriculture (CeRA), ICAR is making available various research journals both closed and open access, published by various scholarly societies and national/international publishers to all the institutes and universities in NARS till June 30, 2014 and afterwards, it would be supported nationally through its plan funds.

Like wise, under another NAIP sub-project - the Indian Agricultural Dissertations Repository, 'Krishi Prabha' is developed in which all the post graduate and doctoral thesis submitted to various agricultural universities during 2000-2009 were digitized and made available to all the institutes and universities in NARS under Internet Protocol (IP) authentication. However all of these are scanned in image format, and are not available in full-text searchable format. One can only search titles, authors and the specified keywords submitted author. The Maharashtra Animal and Fishery Sciences

University is making few of its submitted thesis available for full-text download whereas College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry under Anand Agricultural University is making all of its' 67 thesis as full-text downloads on OpenMED@NIC an open access archive for Medical and Allied Sciences established by National Informatics Centre.

The data sharing is observed to be almost nil in ICAR institutes till NAIP launch.. Under various sub-projects of NAIP Component-1, there are some efforts in this direction of making information and data available for which some guidelines were developed under the AGROWEB – Digital Dissemination System for Indian Agricultural Research (ADDSIAR) sub-project of NAIP. Under this sub-project, IIHR is making available market data in the form of graphs. In entire NARS, the best example for market and weather data sharing is the Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU). It is making available various market locations data as well as weather data of all the districts of Tamilnadu online on its TNAU Agritech Portal. This portal has recently awarded with National Award for e-Governance 2010-2011 by Government of India. The other institutes and universities in NARS are only sharing weather based advisory for various agricultural operations. Every year the Indian Agricultural Statistics Research Institute (IASRI) publishes Agricultural Data This book is available on its website in a PDF format. The data is not in retrievable mode and there is less scope for interoperability of the data to make meaningful analysis and visualizations. The Directorate of Economics and Statistics under Ministry of Agriculture, Government of India is making available all the agricultural statistics in spreadsheets.

Data with respect to germplasm at few ICAR institutes is only restricted to the number of accessions available in a particular genotype/genus on websites. Exception to this is IISR which is making available passport data of all the germplasm on its website which can be accessed by anyone upon registration. The National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources (NBPGR), the national repository of plant genotypes, has created an online platform in association with Food and Agricultural Organisation (FAO) for sharing the information of passport data of various germplasm available at various institutes/universities in India. It has also published Inventory of Registered Crop Germplasm (2009-2010) registered under ICAR system. Digital Herbarium at

Directorate of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants (DMAPR); Digital Library on Bruchids, National Information Sharing Mechanism on Global Plan of Action for Germplasm Conservation, Utilization and Implementation and Information Management System for Biodiversity Conservation, which are hosted at NBPGR website, are aimed at information and data sharing of available germplasm. The National Agricultural Bioinformatics Grid is established at IASRI under NAIP for capturing and sharing genomic data produced in NARS. The Rice Knowledge Management Portal (RKMP) is being developed at Directorate of Rice Research to strengthen the better flow of rice knowledge and information of rice. It is also aimed at development of Data Centre which captures all the All India Networking Rice Research Project spread across various agro-climatic zones of India.

The Indian Institute of Soil Science (IISS), Bhopal has developed, GIS- based Nutrient Status of Soils in India showing soil types, mineral nutrition deficiencies but are only in PDF formats. Similarly, under National Animal Disease Referral Expert Management System (NADRES) of Project Directorate on Animal Disease Monitoring and Surveillance (PDADMAS), Bengaluru, developed GIS maps of disease outbreaks but are only available in PDF format.

II. Organization Policies

Till date, no institute/university had adopted policy on 'Information and Data Sharing' in NARS is noticed. However, under ADDSIAR sub-project, a policy booklet 'Uniformity Guidelines for Agricultural Institutes/Universities Websites' was released to bring about uniformity in the websites and for proper information and data sharing. It advises to use FOSS content management systems for information and data sharing. As it is proposed to establish National Agricultural Data Centre for web hosting and housing information/data sharing products in NARS, it is necessary to formulate a structured policy guidelines on information, data sharing & management that is to be implemented at all levels in NARS system. An Open Access policy similar to Council of Industrial and Scientific Research (CSIR) should be adopted by the ICAR. During the meeting on “Information and Communication Technology in ICAR” on November 29, 2010 at NASC Complex, New Delhi, it was proposed and agreed that the requirements of ICT in ICAR would be worked out in the form of immediate, short term and long term

perspectives and partnerships with private/foreign organisations would be explored for expeditious and time-bound benefits of ICT for the farmers. It was also agreed that all ICAR institutes and SAUs should be linked to CIARD and a strategy for utilization of National Knowledge Network bandwidth would be prepared for knowledge sharing. The standards would also be created and enforced at all levels for data collection, analysis and data sharing. It was also proposed to set up an advisory group to guide ICAR from time to time on various ICT related issues.

III. Obstacles and constraints

The scholarly societies are not tech-savvy still. With the entry of private web-hosting providers, now they are able to make their journals online for wide visibility but no efforts are being made for free availability and accessibility of research articles to all stakeholders without subscription. They fear that they lose revenue and their subscribers and hence, both libraries and individuals prefer printed journals. Similarly, in order to generate revolving fund revenue, most of the ICAR institutes' publications are in print only form and are for sale. The institutes are of the opinion that when publications are made online, none would buy and they would not get back the cost/expenditure incurred on publishing/printing and they cannot make only e-books as the clients/stakeholders need print form too. Not many of the institutes/universities are showing interest to establish its institutional repository to showcase their publications unless there is an advisory and support in the form of a project from ICAR. Lack of a data centre of their own for web hosting, skilled manpower in use and application of modern open source content management software and lack of awareness on the issues of 'availability & accessibility' of information and data with respect to are few other obstacles in information and data sharing in NARS. The existing computer application scientists' potential was not harnessed to the possible extent and were lacking in working as national teams for address issues of ICT in agriculture for information and data sharing. They are all working remotely and now with the change in policy, not to recruit any more scientists at entry level in the field of computer applications in agriculture may add to existing obstacles for free flow and sharing of information/data.

IV. Examples of interoperability

The Eprints@IARI and Eprints@CMFRI are all indexed in BASE (Bielefeld Academic Search Engine), Bielefeld University Library, Germany, ScientificCommons.org project of Institute for Media and Communication Management at the University of St. Gallen, Google Scholar, Scirus, science-specific search engine on the Internet whereas, open access journals are indexed in Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ).

V. Priority areas, current and potential

In India, about 60 open access institutional repositories have been established by various public and private institutes and universities. Only five repositories have been established till date. In NARS, under e-Granth sub-project of NAIP, 12 consortia partners from NARS are in the process of establishment of repositories in which their library collections as well as research publications would be deposited. These repositories should be built on OAI-MHP compliant software and the contents should be made interoperable for further harvesting by search engines viz., Google or Google Scholar to make them available to the world. All the repositories should be made of OAI compliant and awareness workshops should be conducted along with the policy implementation at each and every institute and university.

A database of all the copyright policies of all the publishers in India could also be developed and integrated with SHERPA/RoMEO. With all these efforts, an Open Access NARS Research Database could be made available to the world as National Open Access Periodicals Repository of CSIR or as Asian Journals Online (AsiaJOL) which collects information from the Journals Online (JOL) databases of journals published in Bangladesh, Nepal, The Philippines, Vietnam, Sri Lanka and Indonesia. With regards to the thesis, the ICAR/NARS should adopt the policy of Shodhganga Repository established by Information and Library Network (INFLIBNET) Centre that all theses and dissertations submitted would be available in open access to the academic community world-wide and authors/research scholar/university can impose restrictions on access if so they desire. The INFLIBNET has so far Signed Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with 23 Universities and has ~1748 thesis deposits. When such an open access research landscapes of ICAR/NARS institutes and universities are showcased, they can invite collaborative proposals and the ICAR/NARS should work

towards this goal. The citation & impact analysis metrics should be used for assessment of researchers in the NARS for this ICAR may establish Indian Agriculture Scientific Citation and Impact Analysis Unit at its headquarters. To make agricultural research information publicly available and accessible to all, Agropedia is working and it should be made content rich with reliable information. For this, a national programme may be launched on the lines of Wikipedia and periodic workshops for capacity building and sensitisation should be conducted.

For the entire NARS, a e-commerce ICT project in agriculture on the lines of 'e-krishi' project of the Department of Agriculture, Kerala administered by Kerala IT Mission and oriented towards business and giving market advisory for agriculture and aquaculture for Kerala state should be adopted. An advisory group may be formed to guide ICAR/NARS from time to time on various issues related to information and data sharing. The information and data sharing services with the institutes and universities should be registered with Coherence in Information for Agricultural Research for Development (CIARD) to make them available & accessible. The NARS institutes and universities are present in various agro-climatic zones, this strength should be exploited to build a huge database on agro-meteorology collected over the period of time and with the help of data mining techniques, meaningful analysis could be made out and a reliable micro-level forecasting could be developed. Mapping of biodiversity, biosecurity, diseases, pathogens, etc. should be taken up with integration of Geographical Information System (GIS). There is a need for large scale capacity building at the national level for dissemination of information to the farmers in all local languages. So, the existing Agriculture Research Information System (ARIS) cells in all the institutes and universities should be strengthened with necessary manpower and infrastructure. With the existing various advisories and decision support systems, a robust interlinked ICT Farming Systems could be developed with the integration of infrastructure and contents management.

The following are some of the points that emerged during the meeting on “Information and Communication Technology in ICAR” on November 29, 2010 at New Delhi.

- To make agricultural research information publicly available and accessible to all, ‘Agropedia’ is being developed and it should be made content rich with a reliable information. For this, a national programme may be launched on the lines of Wikipedia and periodic workshops for capacity building and sensitisation should be conducted.
- The information and data sharing services with the institutes and universities should be registered with Coherence in Information for Agricultural Research for Development (CIARD) and an advisory should be formed to guide ICAR/NARS from time to time on various issues related to information and data sharing.
- There is a need for large scale capacity building at the national level for dissemination of information to the farmers in all local languages. So, the existing ARIS cells in all the institutes and universities should be strengthened with necessary manpower and infrastructure.
- With the integration of infrastructure and content management of existing various advisories and decision support systems, a robust interlinked ICT Farming Systems could be developed.
- The NARS system institutes and universities are present in various agro-climatic zones, this strength should be exploited to build a huge database on agro-meteorology collected over the period of time and with the help of data mining techniques, meaningful analysis could be made out and a reliable micro-level forecasting could be developed.
- Mapping of bio-diversity, bio-security, diseases, pathogens, etc should be taken up with GIS.
- The standards should be created and enforced at all levels for data collection, analysis and data sharing and there should be a policy in place which has a system of accountability and reward for data sharing.

All the data of output from various All India Networking Projects (AINP) should be deposited in a central 'Data warehouse' and be made available under a suitable 'Data Licence' in NARS system. The standards should be created and enforced at all levels for data collection, analysis and data sharing and there should be a policy in place which has a system of accountability and reward for data sharing. With the recent changes in

policies across the globe, the Government of India has also planned to share its data. It was announced that a portal <http://data.gov.in> would be established for data sharing on the lines of United States <http://data.gov> and United Kingdom <http://data.gov.uk> in July 2011. This opportunity and platform should be utilized by the NARS system to share their data.

VI. CASE STUDIES

Eprints@CMFRI: An Open Access Repository of CMFRI

The Eprints@CMFRI <<http://eprints.cmfri.org.in>> institutional repository takes a place of special mention in the National Agricultural Research System of India. It was made live on 25 February 2010 by Central Marine Fisheries Research Institute (CMFRI) and since then article were deposited till date it has collection of 8134 records. It has collections since year 1948. This credit mainly goes to the Director, CMFRI and the Librarian, Mr V. Edwin Joseph who has taken special interest to create the repository to house their vast collection of publications. This repository has both open access and closed access publications in its collection. This institution has also so far not declared any open access policy.

Eprints@IARI : An Open Access Repository of IARI

The Eprints@IARI <http://eprints.iari.res.in> is made live by Unit of Simulation and Informatics (USI), Indian Agricultural Research Institute (IARI) on 9th November 2009. From that the time of hosting till date the repository received 226 records of deposits mainly of research articles and conference proceedings and few book chapters. The IARI has so far not adopted an open access policy but the repository was approved to be in place. Frequently, the USI organises sensitisation workshops on open access and how to deposit the publications into the repository. However, the rate of deposition and number of articles are less when compared with other existing repositories. The main reason is the absence of a policy and reward system as expressed by the authors themselves. When there are no issues of copyrights the deposits were made open access otherwise as restricted access only to the registered users of IARI.

Open Access Journal of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants

The Open Access Journal of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants (OAJMAP) <<http://www.oajmap.in>> is a unique journal in NARS. It is the very first journal to be launched as open access journal from a scholarly society housed in an ICAR institute. It was initially supported by Open Knowledge Society, India for hosting online but now it has migrated onto

'epubs' platform of ICAR for more recognition and visibility. It has so far received 11582 page visits as per its webpage counter. But as per the Google analytics, 3,238 visits came from 85 countries/territories from Nov 1, 2010 - Jun 6, 2011. It has 2,550 absolute unique visitors, 16,025 page views and returning visitor were 689 with 14.85 visits/day. It has publishing frequency of two in a year and so far it has published two journal issues. It has received articles from various parts of the world and few from Iran were published. It has successfully organised a nation seminar in the year 2010 and has published selected abstracts in its latest issue [2010 (2)]. The journal is indexed in Scoups, CABI, Chemical Abstracts Service and Open J-Gate etc.

Indian Agricultural Research Journals

The Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR) has made its two journals the Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences and the Indian Journal of Animal Sciences using Open Journal Systems (OJS) software on the platform <<http://epubs.icar.org.in>> as the part of the project E-Publishing System for Knowledge Sharing in Agriculture (EPSKAR), a sub-project under world bank assisted National Agricultural Innovation Project (NAIP). Trivedi et al (2011) reports that the 'epubs' platform has ~6800 registered during last six months (November 2010 – May 2011) there have been more than 60,000 visits as per source Google Analytics. They also report that the platform is getting visitors from 157 countries with the order of top 10 countries India, China, Turkey, Iran, USA, Pakistan, Canada, Mexico, Philippines and Bangladesh. It is reported by the project team that on an average, 15-20% of the total submissions in a day are from international authors (Trivedi et al 2011).

Source: Trivedi, T.P., Himanshu, Aruna T Kumar, Hansraj, Sudhir Pradhan. 2011. E-Enabled Global Knowledge Sharing In Agricultural Research (Un-Published). Available at <<http://docs.docstoc.com/orig/14662786/14fc8e8a-ed79-446b-80c1-a5a153c01277.docx>>

Consortium for e-resources in Agriculture (CeRA)

As a sub-project under National Agricultural Innovation Project, the Consortium for e-resources in Agriculture (CeRA) is providing access to ~2000 journals both closed and open access from its platform Members/members.asp to ~134 institutes and universities in NARS. Apart from this, the non-subscribed journal articles are being made available to various researchers in NARS by Document Delivery Request (DDR). It is conducting various awareness seminars on use of CeRA. It is also providing calculated citation index/h-index by Scopus/ISI Citation Index to researches upon request.

Source: About CeRA. 2010. Chandrasekharan H., Mishra, A.K., Sridhar Gutam, Usha Khemchandani, Rajkumari Kasrija, Shikha Goyal, Sarita Patle and Amit Pandey. 2010. (Un-Published). Available at <<http://www.cera.jccc.in/about/AboutCeRA.pdf>>

International Expert Consultation on
"BUILDING THE CIARD FRAMEWORK FOR DATA AND
INFORMATION SHARING"

Draft Workshop Program

International Expert Consultation on
"Building the CIARD Framework for Data and Information Sharing"

Date: 20-23 June 2011

**Jointly organized by GFAR, FAO, CGIAR & CAAS
Hosted by CAAS**

Language: English

SCHEDULE OF SESSIONS

Opening

Day 1

14:00-14:30	Participant Registration
14:30-18:00	InfoShare Marketplace Marketplace Exhibition and Knowledge Share Fair by participating systems/institutions on experiences, capacities and competencies in managing and sharing AR4D related data and information [Venue: tbd]
18:00	Cocktails

Day 2

07:30-08:30	Participant Registration
08:30-09:30	<u>Session 1:</u> Setting the Stage. Statements from organizers (CAAS, CGIAR, FAO, GFAR) Participant introductions
09:30-10:00	Tea
10.00-11:00	<u>Session 2:</u> Evidence. Introductory Statements by invited experts on outputs from Virtual Forum on "What needs to be shared" and "How can interoperability be achieved". Introduction to objectives and modalities for Working Groups (four)
11:00-11.15	Working Groups: Short presentations (10-15 minutes) from participants in each group will describe some key aspects of experiences to date on in development, uptake and use of information management standards in all types of content in terms of:

- What content is being shared?
- What information management (IM) mechanisms are being used?

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- What capacities (institutional and individual) are required and available?
- As a priority, which subject areas will be benefitted by sharing?
- What are the key points related to developing an interoperability infrastructure?

12:30-14:00	Lunch
14:00-15:30	Plenary: Presentation of outputs from Working Groups, followed by discussion. Facilitators synthesize accumulated outputs.
15:30-15:45	Tea/coffee
15:45-17:30	<u>Session 3</u> : Tools, Standards and Infrastructures - Plenary presentations on status of interoperability standards (derived from Virtual Forum) followed by discussion.
18:00	Dinner

Day 3

09:00-11:00	<u>Session 4</u> : Group Session on Next Steps. Brief summary of outcomes of previous day. Introduction to objectives and modalities of three Working Groups on key themes, drawing on outcomes of previous day: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Theme 1: Advocacy: Aligning policies• Theme 2: Capacity strengthening needs and how to fulfill them• Theme 3: Coherence and Integration of Information Objects
11:00-11:15	Tea/coffee
11:15-12:30	Plenary: Presentation of outputs from Working Groups, followed by discussion. Facilitators synthesize accumulated outputs.
12:30-14:00	Lunch
14:00-17:00	Presentations on examples/cases in sharing AR data (Preparation of key outputs for discussion (core group of facilitators/organizers))
18:00	Dinner

Day 4

09:00-10:30	<u>Session 3</u> : Agendas for Action. Plenary: Presentation and discussion of draft statements of outcomes Area 1: Advocacy – CIARD Task Force and others Area 2: Content Management – Task Force and others
10:30-10:45	Tea/coffee
10:45-12:00	Plenary: Continued discussion of draft statements of outcomes Area 3: Capacity building
12:00-12:30	Statements from Organizers: future events, linking to GCARD process and to other major initiatives.
12:30-14:00	Lunch
14:00-18:00	Optional Field Trip
18:00	Dinner